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ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURAL PARADIGMS AND EFFECTIVENESS OF UNIVERSITY POSTGRADUATE PROGRAMMES

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Abstract

This study questioned whether organizational cultural paradigms prevailing within the state universities facilitate them in providing effective postgraduate (PG) programmes. The study was designed in such a way that data relating to organizational cultural paradigms were obtained from staff members (senior academics and administrative staff) directly responsible for PG programmes (N=400) while data relating to the effectiveness of PG programmes were obtained as actual/true figures from university records. The study was confined to the University of Kelaniya and University of Moratuwa. Overall, the findings suggest that organizational cultural paradigms play a vital role in offering effective PG programmes.

Key words: organizational cultural paradigms, effectiveness of postgraduate programmes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The state university system of Sri Lanka has seen a rapid development in terms of quality of education and geographical distribution. Since the early 1980s, a wave of globalization has been sweeping across the nation changing its economic and social contours and challenging the established socioeconomic systems. With the impact of globalization being felt significantly in social, cultural and economic spheres of Sri Lanka, the university system has become no exception in dealing with its consequences. With the globalization, country has witnessed a boom in numerous privately owned universities and institutions that offer higher education opportunities.

In order to face the challenges posed by changing and challenging environmental conditions, the state university system needs to ensure its long-term self-sustainability and growth. However, the financial resources by way of state financing are insufficient for the university system to achieve its full-potential. Hence, the state universities should generate own financial resources for self-sustainability and growth. However, as part of the government's free education policy, the undergraduate programmes conducted by the state universities have to be offered on non-income

generating basis. Yet, PG programmes can be offered on income generating basis. The other specialized services that can also be offered by the universities and affiliated institutions on income generating basis include consultancy, research and development, testing and certifying. Therefore, the state universities could use PG programmes and other specialized services to ensure the achievement of self-sustainability and growth.

Nevertheless, it is suggested that the state universities are not operating up to their full-potential in offering PG programmes on profit-making basis. In this regard, the literature suggests that any knowledge based organizations have a greater degree of dependence on its human resources and behavioural aspects of its human resources have a greater impact on its success (Cameron, 1986; Karagöz, and Öz, 2008). In order to achieve successful implementation of strategies, there is a range of attributes that must be possessed by human resources, such as commitment, involvement, motivation and willingness to change. Research in this area clearly indicates that cultural paradigms that exist within the organization play a major role in determining the aforementioned attributes of the human resources.

In the above context, this research questions whether organizational cultural paradigms prevailing within the state universities facilitate them in providing effective PG programmes. Therefore, objectives of the study were to 1) investigate the existing level of organizational cultural paradigms, and b) investigate the existing level of effectiveness of PG programmes leading to survival, long term sustainability and growth of PG Programmes, and 2) develop a mechanism to compare organizational cultural paradigms and the effectiveness of PG programmes for strategic decision making.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURAL PARADIGMS

Schein (1992) suggests that culture that prevails within an organization is a manifestation of three components, namely artifacts, values and basic assumptions. Artifacts include the audible and visible behavioural patterns of the organization that includes charts, handbooks, notifications, stories that are quite conspicuous to the observer. Values, which are less conspicuous, are the reasons underlying the behavioural patterns of employees. Basic assumptions, which are typically unconscious in the minds of the individual, are responsible for determining how people perceive, think and feel.

Denison and Mishra (1995) identified four traits of an organizational culture, namely, involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission. According to Denison and Mishra (1995), involvement is the degree of empowerment of its staff, building the organization around teams and develop human capability at all levels. It further indicates commitment to work and feeling of belongingness to the organization (Becker, 1964). People at all levels feel that they have some input to decisions affecting their work, and they also feel that their work is directly connected to the objectives of the organization (Katzenberg, 1993; Spreitzer, 1995).

Consistency is the level of consistence, coordination and integration (Denison and Mishra, 1995); behaviour is rooted in a set of core values, and leaders and followers are skilled at reaching agreement even when there are diverse points of view (Block, 1991). Consistency is a powerful source of stability and internal integration that result from a common mindset and a high degree of conformity (Senge, 1990).

Adaptability is driven by ability to take risks and learn from mistakes, and capability in continuously changing the system to improve the organizations' collective abilities (Nadler, 1998; Senge, 1990).

Mission is the basis for the organization's future and it provides basic direction along which the organization would progress. The mission primarily consists of the environmental opportunities and threats that it will perceive in the environment and its internal strategic intent to offset threats and capitalize opportunities (Denison and Mishra, 1995; Hamel and Prahalad, 1994). A particular culture, at any point of time, could comprise of these four traits in varying degrees (Denison and Mishra, 1995). The literature also indicates that an organizational culture is stable and conservative, and the resistant force that is likely to change a particular culture would be management interventions. The dynamics of culture is the degree of the stability of a given cultural paradigm within the organization or the ability to change the existing cultural paradigm to inculcate a new paradigm to achieve organizational objectives (Denison and Mishra, 1995).

2.2. ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

According Desion et al. (2004), organizational effectiveness emphasizes process control, information management and goal setting. For the purpose of the present study the organizational effectiveness is defined as the extent to which an organization fulfils its objectives (refer to Cameron et al., 1986; Thibodeaus and Favilla, 1995).

With regard to the literature on the effectiveness of higher education institutes, Karagöz, and Öz (2008) state that higher education institutes show a higher level of effectiveness from the individual point of view in realizing objectives for lecturers, but show lower levels of effectiveness at the levels of sub-units and the organization.

Cameron's (1981, 1986) proposed several criteria that can be used to measure effectiveness of higher education institutes under nine fields, namely, student educational satisfaction, student academic development, student career development, student personal development, Faculty and administrator employment satisfaction, professional development and quality of the Faculty, system openness and community

interaction, ability to acquire resources, and organizational health. These dimensions are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Criteria of effectiveness of higher education institutes

Criteria	Description
1. Student educational satisfaction	The extent of satisfaction of students with their educational experiences at the institution
2. Student academic development	The extent of the academic growth, attainment and the progress of students at the institution
3. Student career development	The extent of occupational preparedness of the students, and the emphasis on career development provided by the institution
4. Student personal development	The extent of student development in non-academic, non-career oriented areas, and the emphasis on personal development provided by the institute
5. Faculty and administrator employment satisfaction	The extent of satisfaction of Faculty members and administrators with their employment at the institution
6. Professional development and quality of the faculty	The extent of professional attainment and development of the Faculty provided by the institution
7. System openness and community interaction	The extent of interaction with, adaptation to, and services provided for public by the institution
8. Ability to acquire resources	The ability of the institution to acquire needed resources such as high quality students and faculty and financial support
9. Organizational health	The extent to which internal processes and practices in the institution are smoothly functioning and benevolent

2.3. ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

Several research studies provide evidence for the relationship between organizational culture and effectiveness (Denison and Mishra, 1995; Fey and Denison, 2003; Gillespie et al., 2008). The results of these studies provide evidence for the existence of four cultural traits, i.e., involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission; and studies provide evidence that these traits are positively related to objective and subjective measures of performance.

Specifically, research studies provide evidence that involvement facilitates team work, team efforts, sharing of information and the organization's ability to improve the skill levels of its employees. Further, a higher level of involvement leads to higher levels of motivation in the part of the employees. This higher level of motivation helps employees to achieve higher levels of effectiveness (Becker, 1964; Katzenberg, 1993; Spreitzer, 1995). Consistency indicates well coordinated, and well integrated organizational actions (Davenport, 1993; Saffold, 1988). Behaviour is rooted in a set of core values, and leaders and followers are skilled at reaching agreement even when there are diverse points of view (Block, 1991). This type of consistency is a powerful source of stability and internal integration that results from a common mindset and a high degree of conformity (Senge, 1990).

Adaptable organizations are driven by their customers, take risks and learn from their mistakes, and have capability and experience in creating change (Nadler, 1998; Senge, 1990). Highly adaptable organizations have the capability to respond well to the environmental changes and are capable of evading threats in the environment and capitalise on opportunities. Further, such organizations are continuously changing the system so that they are improving the organizations' collective abilities to provide value for their customers (Stalk, 1988).

Mission is the most vital component in any organization that determines the future of that organization. The mission is based on the long term vision of the organization which provides a clear picture to the employees of all levels with respect to the destination of the origination in the future. The mission is also the foundation stone for setting of organizational objectives that are milestones in the organization's path towards realizing the final vision. The mission should provide a greater degree of motivation for the

employees to lead them along the path towards the achievement of ultimate organizational objectives (Mintzberg, 1987; Ohmae, 1982; Hamel and Prahalad, 1994).

Denison and Mishra (1995) empirically showed that two of the paradigms, involvement and adaptability, are indicators of flexibility, openness, and responsiveness, and were strong predictors of growth. The other two traits, consistency and mission, are indicators of integration, direction, and vision, and were better predictors of profitability. Further, they showed that each of the four traits was also significant in predicting other effectiveness criteria such as quality, employee satisfaction, and overall performance. Overall, these studies conclude that organizational culture is an integral part of the adaptation process of organizations and specific cultural paradigms may be useful in predicting performance and effectiveness.

Based on the literature reviewed above on organizational cultural paradigms, organizational effectiveness, and the relationship between the organizational cultural paradigms and organizational effectiveness, it is proposed for the study that organizational cultural paradigms of the state universities influence the effectiveness of PG programmes. As we were unable to find prior studies investigating the links proposed in this study, after analyzing the data this study intends to develop a mechanism to compare organizational culture and the effectiveness of PG programmes for strategic decision making.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. MEASURES

The organizational cultural paradigms were measured by the four traits proposed by Denison and Mishra (1995), namely, consistency, adaptability, involvement, and mission. The measures are based on Denison and Mishra's standard questionnaire published in Denison and Mishra (1995). As proposed by Denison and Mishra (1995), each trait was measured using 9 items. The responses were on a 5 point Likert Scale (5 = strongly agree, 1 = strongly disagree).

The effectiveness of PG programmes was measured by the nine dimensions adopted from

the criteria proposed by Cameron (1986). These nine items were as follows:

- Q1. Satisfaction of students about PG programmes (perceived in a Likert Scale)
- Q2. Out of the total number of students the % of students with employment in fields related to their PG programmes during the last 3 years (the most likely true figure)
- Q3. The total number of permanent Faculty members on policy making boards or committees during the last 3 years (the most likely true figure)
- Q4. Out of the total number of students registered for PG programmes, the % of students proceeding to MPhil or PhD Programmes during the last 3 years (the most likely true figure)
- Q5. Out of the total number of permanent Faculty members, the number of Faculty members earning a PG Degree or Charter after being hired (the most likely true figure)
- Q6. Out of the total budget allocated to the Faculty/PG Institute, the amount allocated for professional development of academic and administrative staff (in SL Rupees) (the most likely true figure)
- Q7. Number of Faculty members with Doctorates (the most likely true figure)
- Q8. Number of continuous development programmes (where entry qualification is a first degree or an equivalent qualification) provided for public (the most likely true figure)
- Q9. Total Amount of revenue earned by conducting PG programmes (in SL Rupees) (the most likely true figure)

3.2 POPULATION AND SAMPLE

The population of the study comprised of sixteen state owned universities and the PG institutes that are affiliated to these sixteen universities, which come under the umbrella of the University Grants Commission. For the study two universities were selected based on the convenience of data collection. These two universities were the University of Moratuwa (UOM) and the University of Kelaniya (UOK). The UOM specializes predominantly in technology and technical education while the UOK specializes predominantly in pure/natural sciences, management, and social sciences.

For the study, from UOM all the departments of the three Faculties (Faculty of Engineering,

Faculty of Architecture, and Faculty of Information Technology) that provide PG programmes were taken into account. From UOK, all the departments of the three Faculties (Faculty of Social Science and Humanities, Faculty of Science, and Faculty of Commerce and Management [C&M]) and two PG institutes (Post Graduate Institute of Pali and Buddhist Studies [PGIPBS] and Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology [PGIA]) that provide PG programmes were taken into account.

The data was collected from academic and administrative staff of the two universities. Specifically, from each university (representing each Faculty and each department/PG institute) a random sample of 100 academic (Senior Professor to Senior Lecturer) and administrative (Deputy Registrar/Deputy Bursar to Assistant Registrar/Assistant Bursar) staff members who are actively involved in PG programmes were selected. Therefore, from UOM 100 academic and administrative staff members and from UOK 100 academic and administrative staff members who are actively involved in PG programmes responded.

3.3. METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

Two questionnaires were developed for the study. The questionnaire on cultural paradigms was self-administrative in nature and the above mentioned 200 randomly selected academic and administrative staff members responded.

The questionnaire on the effectiveness of PG programmes was developed as a structured interview guide and one of the authors of this paper conducted one-to-one interviews with academic and administrative staff members who were directly involved in and have sufficient knowledge about the PG programmes conducted by each department/PG institute of the each university. During these one-to-one interviews, actual/true data relating to the effectiveness of the PG programmes.

3.4. METHODS OF DATA ANALYSIS

With regard to the data on organizational cultural paradigms, the survey data were analysed using descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test and one-way ANOVA.

The data collected from each department with respect to the effectiveness of PG programmes

were combined to form Faculty-wise figures of seven Faculties of the two Universities. Based on the Faculty-wise figures, nine Faculties/institutes were ranked for the each item (Q1 to Q9 mentioned above) from 1 (Faculty with the highest score for the item) to 9 (Faculty with the lowest score for the item).

4. RESULTS

4.1. LEVEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURAL PARADIGMS

The existing levels of organizational cultural paradigms prevailing in the universities and the results of t-test are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Levels of organizational cultural paradigms - University-wise

Cultural paradigms and university	Mean	S.D.	<i>t</i>	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Involvement	UOM	3.87	.52	3.79	.000
	UOK	3.47	.89		
Consistency	UOM	3.55	.55	2.73	.007
	UOK	3.28	.80		
Adaptability	UOM	3.70	.61	3.78	.000
	UOK	3.29	.86		
Mission	UOM	4.16	.64	6.53	.000
	UOK	3.37	.99		

As shown in Table 1, when the involvement dimension is considered, it is clear that UOM has shown a higher score compared to UOK. Interview data revealed that cultural traits such as team work, team efforts, sharing of information and the organization's ability to improve the skill levels of its employees are playing a major role in UOM. Further, there is a greater degree of interconnectivity among the three Faculties of UOM. For instance, the three Faculties of UOM have common areas, which promote greater team work among staff members of the three Faculties. Interview data, on the other hand, revealed that UOK displays comparatively a low level of emphasis on team work. Further, the responses clearly indicated that there is a low level of interaction between different Faculties. For instance, Faculty of Science may not have anything common with the Faculty of Humanities. As such, the employees of different faculties show lack of requirement to interact. Further, it has been shown that majority of staff members in UOK do

not believe in their ability to make an impact in the university. This can be attributed to the high levels of hierarchical control that has been displayed in its organizational structure. Hierarchical control levels fails to inculcate initiative in the workforce as the control usually tends to be authority oriented in nature.

In terms of consistency, the two universities do not show a major difference between each other. The mean score of the two universities is hovering around 3.5 to 3.3 indicating the comparatively low levels. This indicates that staff members of both the universities lack positive behavioural traits such as capability to consensus through dialogue and negotiations, difficulty in reaching agreements on key issues, common perspective among staff and high degree of compartmentalization. Although these factors are present in both universities, our interview data suggests that the employees of UOM show a comparatively higher levels of consistency related traits. For instance, there is a greater degree of sharing of knowledge and resources among different Faculties. It was also observed that the staff members are in a clear position to discuss matters with each other in a conducive environment with a view of reaching commonly agreed conclusions.

Highly adaptable organizations have the capability to respond well to the environmental changes and are capable of evading threats in the environment and capitalise on opportunities. It is evident that adaptability related cultural traits are present in moderate degrees in both universities. However, our interview data suggests that staff members of UOM have shown considerably high adaptability traits compared to staff members of UOK. For instance, it has been observed that staff members of UOM have displayed high levels of disposition in their ability to respond to environmental factors and change accordingly, ability to respond well to competitors and environment, embark on continuous adaptation and improvement. Furthermore, UOM has shown an enormous potential in changing internally. In addition, the internal organizational structure undergoes adaptations continuously to be able to deliver a wide array of specialized services in fee generating basis. On the other hand, in UOK, apart from the Faculty of Science, the other Faculties have not designed PG programmes to address the needs of the wider-PG student population.

When UOM is considered, its mission related cultural dimension is far superior compared to the UOK. It has been discovered in the responses to interviews that UOM has a long-term purpose and direction. It has a futuristic vision that states “To be the institution of academic excellence in Sri Lanka for technological disciplines with national relevance and international recognition”. The long term purpose and direction is clearly indicated in this statement and the university has been able to rally staff members towards the common purpose. For instance, one of the objectives of the university is to achieve international recognition. Furthermore, based on the vision of the organization, UOM has put in place a range of strategies to reach its ultimate future objectives. Our research reveals that employees are well aware of the vision and objectives and they have an ownership to the vision and are working towards achieving the same. When UOK is considered, the university’s direction is spelt in its vision “The vision of UOK is to be one of the leading universities in Asia, which will prepare internationally competitive graduates, promote values of sustainable society and conduct outstanding research to improve quality of life”. However, staff members have indicated that the goals and the objectives emanating from the vision are ambiguous.

The existing levels of organizational cultural paradigms by Faculty-wise and the results of ANOVA are shown in Table 2 (shown in overleaf). As can be seen from Table 2, there are significant differences between faculties of the two universities.

4.2. LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS OF PG PROGRAMMES

The data for nine effectiveness items were collected as secondary data. These data were ranked ordered for comparison. Table 3 shows the results (shown in overleaf). As can be seen in Table 3, Engineering and Architecture Faculties can be placed on 1st and 2nd positions on a rank of 1 to 9. It is clear from Table 3 that UOM has performed well in terms of:

- (a) Total number of permanent Faculty members on policy-making boards or committees

Table 2. Levels of organizational cultural paradigms - Faculty-wise

		Mean	S.D.	F	Sig	Explanation based on Least Significant Differences (LSD)
Involvement	Engineering	3.83	.49	2.61	.010	Mean differences between: Engineering and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology are significant. Architecture and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology are significant. IT and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and PGIA are significant. Humanities and C&M is significant.
	Architecture	4.00	.61			
	Information Technology	3.91	.78			
	Science	3.50	.85			
	Commerce and Management Studies	3.12	.76			
	Social Sciences	3.44	1.03			
	Humanities	3.73	.81			
	PGIPBS	3.61	.67			
	Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology	3.16	.94			
Consistency	Engineering	3.51	.58	2.14	.034	Mean differences between: Engineering and C&M is significant. Architecture and C&M is significant. IT and C&M is significant. Humanities and C&M is significant. PGIPBS and C&M is significant.
	Architecture	3.63	.45			
	Information Technology	3.66	.63			
	Science	3.29	.68			
	Commerce and Management Studies	2.83	.71			
	Social Sciences	3.23	.91			
	Humanities	3.42	.90			
	PGIPBS	3.87	.67			
	Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology	3.17	.23			
Adaptability	Engineering	3.69	.61	2.56	.011	Mean differences between: Engineering and three Faculties of Science, C&M, and Social Sciences are significant. Architecture and C&M is significant. IT and C&M is significant. Humanities and C&M is significant. PGIA and C&M is significant.
	Architecture	3.61	.52			
	Information Technology	3.19	1.01			
	Science	3.22	.73			
	Commerce and Management Studies	2.79	.61			
	Social Sciences	3.28	.96			
	Humanities	3.52	1.11			
	PGIPBS	3.31	.55			
	Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology	3.59	.43			

Note: Mean differences are significant at the .05 level.

Table 2 continued.

		Mean	S.D.	F	Sig	Explanation based on Least Significant Differences (LSD)
Mission	Engineering	4.15	.63	5.43	.000	Mean differences between: Engineering and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and Humanities are significant. Architecture and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and Humanities are significant. IT and four Faculties of Science, C&M, Social Sciences, and Humanities are significant.
	Architecture	4.07	.70			
	Information Technology	4.13	.54			
	Science	3.29	.76			
	Commerce and Management Studies	3.21	.88			
	Social Sciences	3.43	1.21			
	Humanities	3.33	1.03			
	PGIPBS	3.80	1.12			
	Post Graduate Institute of Archaeology	3.57	.77			

Note: Mean differences are significant at the .05 level.

Table 3: Rank order of cultural paradigms and the effectiveness of PG programmes

Faculty and University	Effectiveness of PG programmes									Cultural paradigms			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Involvement	Consistency	Adaptability	Mission
Engineering, UOM	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	1	2
Architecture, UOM	2	4	2	4	5	2	5	2	4	1	3	1	3
Information Technology, UOM	1	1	7	3	8	2	7	9	4	2	2	1	1
Science, UOK	2	5	4	1	2	2	2	5	8	6	6	8	8
Commerce and Management Studies, UOK	2	3	6	6	2	5	7	8	3	9	9	9	9
Social Sciences, UOK	6	8	3	8	4	5	4	3	2	7	7	7	6
Humanities, UOK	6	9	5	9	6	5	3	4	7	4	5	5	7
PGIPBS, UOK	8	6	9	7	9	9	9	7	6	5	1	6	4
PGIA, UOK	8	7	8	5	7	5	6	5	9	8	8	4	5

Note: For details of Q1 to Q9, refer to measures.

- (b) Number of Faculty members earning a degree or charter after being hired
- (c) The amount of funds allocated for professional development of academic and administrative staff
- (d) Number of Faculty with Doctorates
- (e) Number of continuous development programmes for public, and
- (f) Total amount of revenue earned by conducting PG programmes

4.3. COMPARISON OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURAL PARADIGMS AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PG PROGRAMMES

To compare cultural dimensions with the effectiveness of PG programmes, mean values of cultural dimensions of each Faculty were rank ordered. Table 3 also shows the results of rank ordering of cultural dimensions together with the effectiveness of PG programmes.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study was aimed at identifying the cultural paradigms that exists in two state owned universities in Sri Lanka and to identify the level of effectiveness of PG for strategic decision making. This study has brought into light a less discussed factor of organizational study, namely organizational cultural paradigms. It was revealed that there are four different cultural paradigms prevailing in the universities.

In order to face the challenges posed by the globalization, the state university system needs to ensure its long-term self-sustainability and growth without totally depending on the state financing. Due to the fact that long-term financial self-sustainability and growth are related to the macroeconomic environment, they can be termed as strategic objectives of the universities. Hence, the main objective of the state universities should be to put in place strategies to ensure survival, long-term financial self-sustainability and growth. In this regard, staff members of UOK feel that strategic goals are ambiguous. One of the reasons could be that goals are not well communicated to the employees so that they are not very clear as to what is expected of them. Another reason could be that ambiguous goals create differences in opinion of the staff members. Their differences in opinion make goals difficult to comprehend. The

risk of ambiguous goals is that they can lead to severe failure in the achievement of effectiveness targets as staff members are not clear of their final achievement. Another negative aspect ambiguous goals is that their ability to bring about the much needed motivation of staff members. Modern managerial science clearly identifies that the vision itself should create a high level of motivation for the employees. This will help organizations to place low emphasis on other motivational incentives such as pay, fringe benefits, etc.

One interesting feature about PGIPBS is that it mainly caters for Buddhist higher education. Its PG programme is known to have attracted a large number of foreign students as well as students of other professional disciplines. Our findings reveal that there is a growing demand for this programme from members of the society holding positions in the healthcare sector, banking and financial services sectors and armed forces. As such this is a programme with greater growth potential. However, its lack of adaptability related cultural traits despite having high degree of consistency related cultural traits may lead to low effectiveness levels.

The achievement of self sustainability and growth requires the state universities to develop capabilities to guard against threats that are looming and capitalize on opportunities for its economic benefits. It is within these opportunities that the universities could find avenues for long-term financial self-sustainability and growth. As a result, the state universities should be able to develop capabilities to monitor constantly the macroeconomic environment for opportunities and threats. Further, the state universities should be able to develop strategies to offset threats and capitalize on opportunities for its financial self-sustainability and growth. Furthermore, the state universities have to develop its internal capabilities to be an effective PG programme creator and a disseminator and to function as a vibrant forward looking income generating entity.

Overall, the findings suggest that Faculties with healthy cultural paradigms have more effective PG programmes. Therefore, this study will lay the foundation for future research into other factors influencing PG programme effectiveness and dynamics of existing cultural paradigms. However, future research could include views of

students and other stakeholders of universities to have more data on the effectiveness of PG programmes.

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